

Circadian modulation of behavioural stress indicators varies between diurnal and nocturnal fish species

Santiago Pintos^{a,b,*}, Gonzalo De Alba^b, Tyrone Lucon-Xiccato^a, Francelly Geralda Campos^c, Francisco Javier Sánchez-Vázquez^b, Cristiano Bertolucci^a, Luisa María Vera^b

^a Department of Life Sciences and Biotechnology, University of Ferrara, Ferrara 44121, Italy

^b Department of Physiology, Faculty of Biology, Regional Campus of International Excellence "Campus Mare Nostrum", University of Murcia, Murcia 30100, Spain

^c Laboratory of Animal Biotechnology, Department of Animal Science, Universidade Federal de Viçosa, Viçosa, MG 36570-000, Brazil

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Daily rhythm
Fish behaviour
Stress indicator
Diving test
Tench
Tilapia

ABSTRACT

In the wild, most animals experience daily fluctuations in threats and resources that are synchronised with environmental time cues such as the light-dark cycle. Consequently, animals have evolved daily behavioural patterns (i.e., diurnal or nocturnal) that enhance their fitness by, for example, reducing the temporal overlapping with predators. In fish, previous studies revealed stronger physiological stress responses during the resting period of the species. However, little is known about the circadian modulation of stress indicators and how they are influenced by daily behavioural patterns. In this research, we investigated the behavioural stress responses of two farmed fish species with different activity patterns: the diurnal Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and the nocturnal tench (*Tinca tinca*). To this end, we examined the behavioural response of individuals exposed to the diving test every 4 h over a 24 h cycle (n = 12 fish/species/time point). Results indicated that most behavioural indicators varied according to the time of day, aligning with the daily rhythmic pattern of the two species. Tilapia exhibited stronger stress responses to novelty during the dark phase, while tench displayed higher stress during the light phase. This was supported by stress-related behaviours such as freezing and erratic movements (in both tilapia and tench) and bottom-dwelling (in tench only). These results indicated that stress responses peaked during the resting phase of each species, although behavioural indicators exhibiting this daily variation did not completely coincide between the studied species. Overall, these findings suggest interspecific differences in the daily modulation of behavioural stress indicators in farmed fish, an effect with potential relevance for welfare. Understanding the activity rhythmic patterns, resting periods, and associated daily variation in stress for each fish species of interest can precisely help tailor farming procedures to minimise suffering.

1. Introduction

In nature, both threats (e.g. predation risk) and resources (e.g. food availability) often occur with predictable likelihood over the course of the day (Alanära and Brännäs, 1997; Bécares et al., 2015). This cyclic oscillation is generally synchronised with environmental time cues, such as the light-dark cycle determined by the 24 h period of the Earth's rotation on its axis (Zhdanova and Reeb, 2005). Environmental variables can thereby act as predictive signals for animals, allowing them to adjust their behaviour in advance and effectively cope with daily challenges. Consequently, most animals have evolved internal biological clocks and circadian activity rhythms that ultimately enhance their fitness by, for example, exploiting temporal niches with lower predation

risk (Botts et al., 2020; Monterroso et al., 2013; Tambling et al., 2015). For instance, nocturnal birds typically face high predation risk during daylight hours and prefer to forage at night (Kotler et al., 1991; McNeil et al., 1993; Metcalfe et al., 1998). Similarly, zooplankton species commonly exhibit daily migration patterns across the water column that are driven by predator avoidance strategies (Haney, 1988; Fischer and Visbeck, 1993). This evidence supports the idea that circadian behavioural patterns evolved to trade-off between avoiding threats and exploiting environmental resources (Hammond et al., 2018; Vaze and Sharma, 2013).

In fish, field studies showed that diurnal species avoided foraging activities during the day in presence of predators (Fraser et al., 2004). Moreover, several experiments have documented that physiological

* Corresponding author at: Department of Life Sciences and Biotechnology, University of Ferrara, Ferrara 44121, Italy
E-mail address: santiago.pintos@unife.it (S. Pintos).

stress responses plastically varied according to the time of the day in fish (Figueiredo et al., 2020; López-Olmeda et al., 2013; Vera et al., 2014). Regarding the behavioural facets of responses to stress, evidence suggests similar daily modulation, although this has only been demonstrated in a diurnal model species, the zebrafish *Danio rerio* (Hamilton, 1822; Pintos et al., 2023). Considering that circadian modulation of stress behaviour has been reliably observed in mammals (Bilu and Kronfeld-Schor, 2013; Verma et al., 2010), we expect that other fish species, including those relevant to aquaculture, also display such effect. Moreover, we predict that circadian modulation of behavioural stress responses may vary according to the daily activity pattern of a fish species (i.e., nocturnal or diurnal). Considering that behavioural indicators have recently grown in importance to assess fish welfare (Browning, 2023; Cachat et al., 2010; Martins et al., 2012) and that the influence of biological rhythms on fish stress has been studied using physiological indicators (Gregory, 2022; Pintos et al., 2023; Sánchez-Vázquez et al., 2019), it is important to gather more data on daily variation in stress behaviour in diurnal and nocturnal fish.

In this research, we investigated how the behavioural stress response of two fish species with opposed activity patterns varies throughout the day. Our study species were the Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1758), diurnal (Fortes-Silva et al., 2010) and farmed worldwide for alimentary purposes, and the tench *Tinca tinca* (Linnaeus, 1758), nocturnal (Herrero et al., 2003) and farmed for both food production and conservation purposes (Flajshans et al., 2010; Gela et al., 2006). In the present research, we initially analysed the activity patterns of the two species in the housing conditions to confirm their daily activity pattern. We then examined the behavioural stress response of the two species using the diving test at different times of the day (i.e., every 4 h over a 24 h cycle). The diving test has been reliably used to assess acute stress in teleost species by assessing how individuals behave in a novel and potentially threatening arena (Ansai et al., 2016; Cachat et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2023). This assessment involves analysing behavioural traits potentially associated with stress such as freezing, swimming activity, erratic movements and bottom-dwelling (Blaser and Roseberg, 2012; Tran and Gerlai, 2016). We hypothesised that: 1) behavioural stress responses follow daily rhythmicity in both species; and 2) the circadian modulation of stress behaviour differs between the two species according to their daily activity pattern.

2. Materials and methods

The present research was conducted in the facilities of the Department of Physiology at the University of Murcia (Spain). Fish were reared following Spanish legislation on Animal Welfare and Laboratory Practices. Experimental protocols were performed following the Guidelines of the European Union (2010/63/UE) and Spanish legislation (RD 53/2013 and Law 32/2007) for the use of laboratory animals. They were also approved by the Committee of the University of Murcia on Ethics and Animal Welfare (A13230303).

2.1. Experimental subjects and housing

Juvenile Nile tilapia (length: 3.61 ± 0.75 cm; $n = 112$) and tench (length: 4.83 ± 0.86 cm; $n = 112$) were reared separately in the fish facility of the University of Murcia. The tilapia subjects were obtained through the spawning of adult individuals originally acquired from a global aquaculture company (Fishgen, Swansea, Wales, UK). Tench were purchased at the fry stage from a commercial supplier (Tencas-Atanasio S. L., Badajoz, Spain). Before the experiments, fish were kept in housing tanks in the facility ($28 \times 25 \times 16$ cm; 11 L) in groups of 12 individuals. The tanks were maintained at a constant temperature (26 ± 1 °C for tilapia and 21 ± 1 °C for tench) and exposed to a 12:12 h light-dark (LD) artificial photoperiod (SOLBRIGHT®, LED Flex Strip 1043-W, Rayte, S. L., Murcia, Spain) with lights on at 09.00 a.m. ("zeitgeber" time 0; ZT0). The water in the tanks was constantly aerated and filtered by mechanical

and biological filters.

All the fish were fed a commercial diet (Skretting® Gemma Wean) during the active phase of the species to avoid influencing their natural activity rhythm (López-Olmeda and Sánchez-Vázquez, 2010), varying the exact administration time. Thus, food was administered to tilapia during the light phase (ZT0 to ZT12) and to tench during the dark phase (ZT12 to ZT23).

All housing tanks were equipped with one infrared photocell (Omron, mod E3S-AD62, Kyoto, Japan) to record the locomotor activity of experimental subjects before conducting the behavioural experiments. Photocells were placed in the centre of the front wall of housing tanks and were connected to a computer. Every time a fish interrupted the infrared light beam, they produced an output signal that was recorded and stored in 10-minute intervals using specialized software (DIO98USB; University of Murcia, Spain).

2.2. Experimental design

Seventy-two fish from each species were individually assayed in the behavioural test at different times of the day. Each subject was randomly assigned to one of the following testing time points: ZT2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22. This resulted in 6 groups of 12 fish tested every 4 h for each species ($n = 12$ fish/species/ZT). ZT2 corresponded to 2 h after light on. Each subject was experimentally naive and was tested only once.

2.3. Apparatus

The experimental apparatus was built following previous studies, aiming to maintain the fish-to-tank size ratio typically used for the diving test (Blaser and Roseberg, 2012; Cachat et al., 2010; Maximino et al., 2012; Pintos et al., 2021). It consisted of a glass aquarium ($25 \times 15 \times 15$ cm) and was filled with 13 cm of dechlorinated tap water. Because the walls of the apparatus were made of glass, it was possible to observe the behaviour of the fish from the side, as necessary in this test. For this purpose, a digital webcam (Logitech Webcam C300-1.3MP, Switzerland) was located 40 cm from one wall of the experimental apparatus. The webcam was connected to a laptop to store the recordings. This specific webcam model is sensitive to infrared light. Therefore, to allow recording during the dark phase, an infrared back-light panel (Cebek 2290, Electronica Merchan S.L., Spain) irradiated the apparatus from behind (Fig. 1). Moreover, a white LED strip (6500 K, AquaRay, Tropical Marine Centre, United Kingdom) was placed above the experimental apparatus, providing visible light to the subjects tested during light-hour trials (ZT2, ZT6, and ZT10). The LED strip was turned off in the trials conducted during the dark phase (ZT14, ZT18, and ZT22).

2.4. Testing procedure

The experimental subject was first gently collected with a net from its maintenance aquarium. It was then transported into the diving test apparatus using an opaque jar filled with water. The opaque jar was used to minimise transportation stress. The subject was directly released into the experimental apparatus by slowly emptying the jar. The spontaneous behaviour of the subject was immediately recorded after release for 10 minutes (Tran and Gerlai, 2016). The water was changed between each trial to prevent exposure to the chemical cues produced by the previous experimental subject.

2.5. Analysis of the behavioural indicators

After completion of the experiment, the video recordings were moved into another computer equipped with the software Ethovision XT® (Noldus Information Technology). The software was used to track the position of the subject in the experimental apparatus for the entire test. The xy coordinates of the subject's position were used to calculate a

Fig. 1. Illustrative scheme of the experimental apparatus and design. Juveniles from both species (Nile tilapia and tench) were subjected to the diving test at different times of the day, every 4 h throughout a 24 h cycle ($n = 12$ fish/species/ZT). Fish behaviour was recorded for 10 min and consecutively tracked with Ethovision XT software. The experimental arena ($25 \times 15 \times 15$ cm) was illuminated with a LED strip from above during daylight hours (ZT0–12) and by an infrared light panel from behind (ZT0–23).

set of four dependent variables typically used to measure fish anxiety-like and stress behaviour. The first variable obtained was the time spent in the lower half of the apparatus (hereafter 'bottom-dwelling'). This is the main behavioural indicator developed for this test (Blaser and Roseberg, 2012; Cachat et al., 2010; Maximino et al., 2010). The fish were expected to spend more time in the bottom sector of the apparatus, which is probably perceived as safer, during the ZTs when stress was higher. The second variable analysed was the distance moved (in cm), a typical proxy of locomotor activity in fish (Levin et al., 2007). A second indicator of activity collected was the time spent motionless ('freezing'), calculated using a minimum threshold speed of 0.5 cm/s for tilapia and 0.7 cm/s for tench. Freezing is a typical antipredator behaviour used by small fish such as the zebrafish (Egan et al., 2009). Freezing thresholds were scaled according to fish body size (Pintos et al., 2023). Last, the software provided the angular velocity of the path ('erratic movement'), which is often assumed to increase in stressful situations (Blaser et al., 2010).

The output of the behavioural analysis was extracted both across the overall testing time (10 min) and separately for each minute of the testing. This latter type of repeated measures data allowed us to statistically consider the fact that the obtained behavioural indicators are indeed known to vary due to habituation with the testing apparatus (Blaser and Roseberg, 2012; Wong et al., 2010).

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed in R Statistical software version 4.0.1 (The R foundation for Statistical Computing Vienna Austria <http://www.r-project.org>). Data from both species were analysed with the same pipeline. Locomotor activity records from housing tanks were

analysed by El-Temps software (Version 1, 192; © Prof. Díez-Noguera, University of Barcelona) to generate actograms. Cosinor analysis was conducted on these data to determine whether the daily activity patterns of tilapia and tench fitted the cosine function. All the behavioural indicators analysed in the diving test were also subjected to the Cosinor analysis to evaluate the existence of daily rhythmicity. This was done on the entire testing time. The Cosinor analysis was conducted with the 'cosinor2' R package (Mutak, 2018). Cosinor analysis employs least-squares regressions to model cosine curves, which are useful to describe daily variations (Nelson, 1979), and estimate a rhythm through a zero-amplitude test. In this analysis, a $p < 0.05$ constitutes evidence for a statistically significant rhythm in the given period of time under consideration (i.e., 24 h). Rhythm parameters such as mesor, acrophase and amplitude were also calculated for each behaviour with significant rhythmicity. All acrophases were corrected to locate them in the correct quadrant (Cornélissen and Halberg, 2014) and subsequently transformed from radians to time values (i.e., ZT).

The behavioural indicators were further analysed using linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) to investigate the effect of ZT and variation throughout the duration of the test. The LMMs were run with the 'lme' function of the 'nlme' R package (Pinheiro et al., 2017). The effect of ZT (6 levels: 2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22) and testing minute (1, 2...10) were modelled as fixed effects. Given the presence of repeated observations per each subject (i.e., the different minutes of testing), subject ID was modelled as random effect. Significant differences between ZTs were investigated using post-hoc analysis (Tukey HSD test). The models' assumptions were verified by the Shapiro-Wilk test and Q-Q plot (normality) and by Levene's test (homoscedasticity). Behavioural data that did not meet the assumptions were transformed to improve fitting as follows: square root (activity and freezing in tench and activity in

tilapia), rankit (bottom-dwelling in tench), logarithmic (angular velocity in tench and angular velocity and freezing in tilapia) or square (bottom-dwelling in tilapia) functions. For the variable bottom dwelling, we also used one-sample *t* test to compare the percentage of time spent in the bottom sector of the apparatus versus that expected by chance (i.e. 50 %).

3. Results

3.1. Tilapia

3.1.1. Daily locomotor activity pattern

In housing tanks, tilapia displayed most of their locomotor activity during the light phase (72.16 ± 0.17 %; mean \pm standard error). This diurnal activity pattern was supported by the Cosinor analysis, indicating the presence of significant daily rhythms ($p < 0.01$) with an

acrophase located close to the middle of the light phase (ZT = 5.38; Fig. 2A and B).

3.1.2. Bottom dwelling

On average, tilapia exposed to the diving test spent 79.44 ± 5.24 % of the testing time in the lower sector of the apparatus. This indicated that tilapia spent more time in the bottom sector than expected in case of random movements across the arena (one sample *t*-test: $t_{71} = 16.35$, $p < 0.01$), denoting the expected fish bottom-dwelling response to the diving test. This behaviour did not exhibit significant daily variations (Cosinor: $p = 0.07$; Fig. 3A).

The LMM analysis found a significant main effect of testing minute on bottom dwelling ($F_{9,588} = 5.24$, $p < 0.01$), indicating decreased time in the lower half of the arena over testing time (Fig. S1A). No significant effect of ZT ($F_{5,66} = 1.30$, $p = 0.27$) and no interaction between factors (i.e., ZT and testing time) ($F_{45,588} = 1.04$, $p = 0.40$) were observed for

Fig. 2. Average daily locomotor activity and representative actograms of tilapia (A and C) and tench (C and D) exposed to a 12:12 h light-dark (LD) photoperiod in housing tanks. Locomotor activity is plotted as mean \pm standard error ($n = 5$ tanks/species) and the wave area represents the predicted data for significant Cosinor models. Actograms are double-plotted on a time scale of 48 hours. The height of each point represents the number of infrared light beam interruptions in 10 min over 24 h cycles. Horizontal lines correspond to the last 14 days of housing activity before the day of experiments, represented along the ordinate axis. White and black bars above each graph represent light and dark phases, respectively.

Fig. 3. Daily variation of tilapia behaviour in the diving test. **A.** Bottom-dwelling. **B.** Activity. **C.** Freezing. **D.** Erratic movement. Data points represent mean \pm standard error. Different letters indicate statistical differences between circadian time by means of Tukey HSD test performed on linear mixed models. Wave area plots represented predicted data based on significant Cosinor models. White and black bars above each graph represent light and dark phases, respectively.

this behaviour.

3.1.3. Activity

Tilapia travelled on average 1027.38 ± 188.07 cm during the diving test. Cosinor analysis revealed that tilapia did not exhibit significant daily activity rhythms in response to the diving test (Cosinor: $p = 0.051$; Fig. 3B).

A significant main effect of testing minute was observed on activity behaviour ($F_{9,588} = 18.09$, $p < 0.01$). This effect indicated that tilapia increased activity over testing time (Fig. S1B). Conversely, the main effect of ZT on activity was not significant ($F_{5,66} = 2.29$, $p = 0.055$), and there was not significant interaction between ZT and testing time ($F_{45,588} = 1.05$, $p = 0.38$).

3.1.4. Freezing

On average, tilapia displayed freezing behaviour for 30.70 ± 9.26 % of the test. Cosinor analysis found a significant daily rhythm for freezing behaviour ($p = 0.02$; Fig. 3C), revealing an acrophase located approximately in the middle of the dark phase (ZT = 17.35).

The LMM found a significant effect of testing minute on this

behaviour ($F_{9,588} = 12.54$, $p < 0.01$), indicating decreased freezing over testing time (Fig. S1C). This effect was not related to ZT, since the interaction between this factor and testing time was not significant ($F_{45,588} = 0.93$, $p = 0.60$). Similarly, the main effect of ZT on freezing behaviour was not significant ($F_{5,66} = 2.14$, $p = 0.07$).

3.1.5. Erratic movement

On average, tilapia showed an angular velocity of 170.1 ± 31.4 deg/s. Cosinor analysis found a significant daily rhythm for this variable ($p = 0.03$; Fig. 3D), with an acrophase approximately at the end of the dark phase (ZT = 22.57).

A significant main effect of testing minute was observed on erratic movement behaviour ($F_{9,588} = 3.48$, $p < 0.01$). This effect indicated decreased angular velocity over testing time (Fig. S1D). Conversely, the main effect of ZT on this behaviour was not significant, although it approached the significance threshold ($F_{5,66} = 2.29$, $p = 0.055$; Fig. 3D). Furthermore, the interaction between ZT and testing time was not significant ($F_{45,588} = 1.20$, $p = 0.17$).

3.2. Tench

3.2.1. Daily locomotor activity pattern

Tench displayed most of their locomotor activity in housing tanks during the dark phase ($88.75 \pm 0.60\%$). This nocturnal activity pattern was supported by the Cosinor analysis, indicating the existence of a significant daily rhythm of activity ($p < 0.01$) with an acrophase located close to the middle of the dark phase (ZT = 17.41; Fig. 2C and D).

3.2.2. Bottom dwelling

Overall, tench spent $88.58 \pm 10.97\%$ of the testing time in the lower half of the experimental arena. This percentage was higher than expected in case of random movements (one sample *t*-test: $t_{71} = 20.80$, $p < 0.01$), denoting the expected bottom-dwelling response to the diving test. Cosinor analysis showed that this bottom dwelling exhibited significant daily variations ($p < 0.01$; Fig. 4A), showing maximum values close to the middle of the light phase (acrophase: ZT = 6.24).

The LMM found a significant main effect of ZT ($F_{5,66} = 12.32$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that tench spent more time in the lower half of the apparatus during the light phase compared to the dark phase (Tukey: Fig. 4A). A significant effect of testing minute was also observed ($F_{9,592} = 14.97$, $p < 0.01$) along with a significant interaction between testing minute and ZT ($F_{45,592} = 2.16$, $p < 0.01$). This indicated that bottom dwelling decreased over testing time only for ZT 14, 18 and 22 (Fig. 4B).

3.2.3. Activity

On average, tench travelled 1023.99 ± 695.74 cm during the test. Cosinor analysis revealed daily rhythmicity for this parameter ($p < 0.01$; Fig. 4C) with an acrophase located approximately in the middle of the dark phase (ZT = 18.25).

The LMM analysis on activity found a significant main effect of ZT ($F_{5,66} = 27.78$, $p < 0.01$), indicating higher activity in the dark phase compared to the light phase (Tukey: Fig. 4C). This analysis also detected variation in this behaviour over testing time ($F_{9,592} = 6.10$, $p < 0.01$), with activity values increasing over the course of the test (Fig. S2A). This effect was independent from ZT, since the interaction between both factors (i.e., testing time and ZT) was not significant ($F_{45,592} = 2.16$, $p = 0.45$).

3.2.4. Freezing

Tench displayed freezing behaviour for $46.28 \pm 31.73\%$ of the testing time. Cosinor analysis showed that this behaviour exhibited a daily rhythm ($p < 0.01$; Fig. 4D). The acrophase of freezing behaviour was approximately in the middle of the light phase (ZT = 6.48).

A significant main effect of ZT was found on this behaviour ($F_{5,66} = 31.34$, $p < 0.01$), indicating increased freezing in the light phase compared to the dark phase (Tukey: Fig. 4D). Freezing also varied across testing time ($F_{9,592} = 10.41$, $p < 0.01$), showing decreased values over the course of the test (Fig. S2B). The interaction between testing time and ZT was not significant ($F_{45,592} = 0.84$, $p = 0.75$), revealing independent main effects of both ZT and testing time on freezing.

3.2.5. Erratic movement

Tench showed an average angular velocity of 223.9 ± 107.7 deg/s. Cosinor analysis found significant daily rhythms for this measure of erratic movements ($p < 0.01$; Fig. 4E), showing an acrophase located approximately in the middle of the light phase (ZT = 7.03).

The LMM analysis on erratic movement found a significant main effect of ZT ($F_{5,66} = 16.45$, $p < 0.01$), mostly due to increased angular velocity in the light phase compared to the dark phase (Tukey: Fig. 4E). There was also a significant variation due to testing time ($F_{9,592} = 1.91$, $p = 0.04$), indicating decreased erratic movement over testing time (Fig. S2C). This effect was independent from ZT, because the interaction between testing time and ZT was not significant ($F_{45,592} = 0.86$, $p = 0.72$).

4. Discussion

This research investigated the daily variation in behavioural stress responses in two teleost fish species with opposed daily activity patterns: the diurnal Nile tilapia and the nocturnal tench. Most of the behavioural indicators analysed showed variation throughout the day, aligning with the intraspecific differences in temporal habits. Furthermore, although all analysed traits varied over testing time and suggested habituation in both species, our findings revealed that behavioural stress indicators did not completely overlap between species. This underscores the importance of developing species-specific stress indicators to enhance welfare assessment in fish.

In Nile tilapia, significant daily variation was observed in two behavioural traits: freezing and erratic movement. Both indicators peaked during the dark phase. As higher freezing and erratic movements are typically associated with increased stress in fish (Blaser et al., 2010; Egan et al., 2009; Pintos, 2024), this suggests that Nile tilapia experienced greater stress at night. This finding is consistent with an earlier study in zebrafish, another diurnal species, where behavioural stress responses were higher during the night (Pintos et al., 2023). Consistent with previous studies, these results also supported the use of specific behavioural traits (i.e., freezing and erratic movements) as reliable stress markers for Nile tilapia (Pintos et al., 2024).

Notably, the data collected from tilapia suggested a similar trend in the two remaining indicators, although the lack of statistical significance (*p*-values between 0.05 and 0.07) warrants cautious interpretation. These findings on bottom dwelling and activity hint that the stress peak occurred during the dark phase but may extend into the early hours of the light phase. However, activity data can be challenging to interpret due to the influence of multiple factors. For instance, in a novel environment, tilapia might exhibit reduced activity at night due to stress, but also high activity levels unrelated to stress during the day, such as those due to exploration and searching for novel food resources. Critically, our records of housing locomotor activity confirmed previous studies supporting that tilapia exhibited diurnal activity rhythms (Fortes-Silva et al., 2010). This finding suggested that the diving test exposure impaired activity rhythms in tilapia and supported this proxy as a sensitive indicator of stress in our study. In agreement, several studies showed that distinct stressors can disrupt circadian processes across taxa, including fish. For example, defeating social stress has been shown to reduce daily locomotor activity by up to 50% in adult mice (Ota et al., 2018). Social isolation can lead to phase shifts and prolonged activity periods in birds (Chaturvedi et al., 2024). In fish, altered activity and sleep patterns have been reported in response to environmental stressors such as chemical and light pollution (Silva et al., 2022), effects that are similarly observed in birds and rodents (Sanders et al., 2021; Thoré et al., 2024). Collectively, this evidence supports disrupted behavioural rhythms as potential stress markers in vertebrates.

The results obtained in tench fully supported our working hypothesis. This species exhibited daily variation in all behavioural indicators analysed. Activity was higher during the night, which could be attributed to either lower basal activity levels during the day or higher stress response at night, as discussed for the tilapia. Nevertheless, our records of daily locomotor activity showed that tench also displayed nocturnal activity patterns in housing conditions. This finding aligns with previous studies supporting tench as a strictly nocturnal species (Herrero et al., 2003; Vera et al., 2005) and, unlike tilapia, suggested that activity may act as a locomotion proxy rather than a stress indicator in this species.

The remaining three indicators (i.e., bottom dwelling, freezing and erratic movements), more reliably associated with stress in several teleost species (Blaser et al., 2010; Blaser and Roseberg, 2012; Chin et al., 2018; Maximino et al., 2010; Qiu et al., 2017; Thompson et al., 2016), consistently indicated higher stress during the light phase in tench. Indeed, data on the temporal variation within the test supported this conclusion, showing that bottom-dwelling remained unchanged during daylight hours but decreased significantly over time at night.

Tench

Fig. 4. Daily variation and habituation of tench behaviour in the diving test. A. and B. Bottom-dwelling. C. Activity. D. Freezing. E. Erratic movement. Data points represent mean \pm standard error. Different letters indicate statistical differences between ZTs by means of Tukey HSD test performed on linear mixed models. Asterisks indicate statistical differences between testing minutes on bottom-dwelling behaviour. Wave area plots represented predicted data based on significant Cosinor models. White and black bars above each graph represent light and dark phases, respectively.

This would further suggest a stronger stress response during the light phase (Wong et al., 2010).

Our findings generally support the initial predictions of this study: behavioural responses to stress in fish vary throughout the day according to their diurnal or nocturnal habits. This effect is likely an adaptation evolved to cope with daily fluctuations of threats, such as predation risk (Fraser et al., 2004; Fraser et al., 1993; Hammond et al., 2018). While our findings may represent the general pattern of diurnal and nocturnal species, further studies should gather data from other fish species with different temporal habits to confirm this hypothesis. Moreover, it is worth considering that some species, might exhibit different stress peaks, such as during the light change phases.

From an applied perspective, our work strongly supports the need to consider circadian variation to improve fish welfare in captivity. For instance, if potentially stressful procedures such as transport and sorting are performed during a time of the day that corresponds to a low peak of stress, the resultant welfare decrease might be moderate. Even simple procedures such as delivery of food might bring negative consequences if performed in the wrong period of the day (e.g. when the stress is higher). The rhythmicity observed in this study should also be considered in polyculture aquaculture systems. Species with contrasting temporal habits may require distinct handling schedules and therefore, may be difficult to farm in the same facility without welfare consequences.

Another relevant issue raised by our study concerns the behavioural indicators. The interspecific variation found suggests that further research is necessary to identify species-specific stress indicators. It is worth noting that most of the indicators collected in this study have been recently explored in farmed fish species such as the European seabass *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Linnaeus 1758), the seabream *Sparus aurata* (Linnaeus 1758), or the coho salmon *Oncorhynchus kisutch* (Walbaum, 1792) (Alfonso et al., 2020; Hamilton et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2024) and are simple to monitor in farm conditions, even with automatic tracking software (Pinkiewicz et al., 2011). This should favour research on different species.

Our findings also raise a potential issue concerning the results of applied research that uses behavioural paradigms such as the diving test. Various fish species are commonly employed in ecotoxicology studies using these behavioural tests, and it is already known that the time of day when the test is performed might affect the assessment results (Krylov et al., 2021; Thoré et al., 2021). These results suggest that each species requires specific consideration, highlighting the importance of tailoring research methods to the unique circadian patterns of the target species being studied to avoid confounding results.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Santiago Pintos: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tyrone Luon-Xiccato:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Gonzalo De Alba:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Francisco Javier Sánchez-Vázquez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Francelly Geralda Campos:** Methodology, Investigation. **Luisa María Vera:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Cristiano Bertolucci:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was performed within “EASYTRAIN” network supported by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action framework under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme [H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020, grant agreement N° 956129] (to S.P, C.B and F.J.S.V). L.M.V. was awarded a “Ramón y Cajal” fellowship [RYC-2017–21835] by the Spanish MINECO/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 cofunded by “ESF Investing in your future”. F.G.C was awarded a ‘Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel – Brazil (CAPES)’ fellowship [Financing Code 001].

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.applanim.2024.106458.

References

- Alanärä, A., Brännäs, E., 1997. Diurnal and nocturnal feeding activity in Arctic char (*Salvelinus alpinus*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Can. J. Fish. Aquat. Sci.* 54 (12), 2894–2900.
- Alfonso, S., Sadoul, B., Cousin, X., Bégout, M.L., 2020. Spatial distribution and activity patterns as welfare indicators in response to water quality changes in European sea bass, *Dicentrarchus labrax*. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 226, 104974.
- Ansai, S., Hosokawa, H., Maegawa, S., Kinoshita, M., 2016. Chronic fluoxetine treatment induces anxiolytic responses and altered social behaviors in medaka, *Oryzias latipes*. *Behav. Brain Res.* 303, 126–136.
- Bécares, J., García-Tarrasón, M., Villero, D., Bateman, S., Jover, L., García-Matarranz, V., Sanpera, C., Arcos, J.M., 2015. Modelling terrestrial and marine foraging habitats in breeding Audouin’s gulls *Larus audouinii*: timing matters. *PLoS One* 10 (4), e0120799.
- Bilu, C., Kronfeld-Schor, N., 2013. Effects of circadian phase and melatonin injection on anxiety-like behavior in nocturnal and diurnal rodents. *Chronobiol. Int.* 30 (6), 828–836.
- Blaser, R.E., Roseberg, D.B., 2012. Measures of anxiety in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*): dissociation of black/white preference and novel tank test. *PLoS One* 7 (5), e36931.
- Blaser, R.E., Chadwick, L., McGinnis, G.C., 2010. Behavioral measures of anxiety in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *Behav. Brain Res.* 208 (1), 56–62.
- Botts, R.T., Eppert, A.A., Wiegman, T.J., Blankenship, S.R., Rodriguez, A., Wagner, A.P., Mooring, M.S., 2020. Does moonlight increase predation risk for elusive mammals in Costa Rica? *Trop. Conserv. Sci.* 13, 1940082920952405.
- Browning, H., 2023. Improving welfare assessment in aquaculture. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 10, 1060720.
- Cachat, J., Stewart, A., Grossman, L., Gaikwad, S., Kadri, F., Chung, K.M., Kalueff, A.V., 2010. Measuring behavioral and endocrine responses to novelty stress in adult zebrafish. *Nat. Protoc.* 5 (11), 1786–1799.
- Chaturvedi, K., Srivastava, A., Malik, S., Rani, S., 2024. The presence/absence of conspecifics modulates the circadian locomotor activity and body mass in spotted muntia (*Lonchura punctulata*). *Chronobiol. Int.* 41 (1), 105–126.
- Chin, J.S., Gassant, C.E., Amaral, P.M., Lloyd, E., Stahl, B.A., Jaggard, J.B., Duboue, E.R., 2018. Convergence on reduced stress behavior in the Mexican blind cavefish. *Dev. Biol.* 441 (2), 319–327.
- Cornélissen, G., & Halberg, F. (2014). *Chronomedicine*. Wiley StatsRef: Statistics Reference Online.
- Egan, R.J., Bergner, C.L., Hart, P.C., Cachat, J.M., Canavello, P.R., Elegante, M.F., Kalueff, A.V., 2009. Understanding behavioral and physiological phenotypes of stress and anxiety in zebrafish. *Behav. Brain Res.* 205 (1), 38–44.
- Figueiredo, F., Aragão, C., Pinto, W., Dinis, M.T., Oliveira, C.C., 2020. Optimizing rearing and welfare in Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) broodstock: Effect of ambient light intensity and handling time on stress response. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 222, 104880.
- Fischer, J., Visbeck, M., 1993. Seasonal variation of the daily zooplankton migration in the Greenland Sea. *Deep Sea Res. Part I: Oceanogr. Res. Pap.* 40 (8), 1547–1557.
- Flajshans, M., Gela, D., Kocour, M., Buchtová, H., Rodina, M., Pšenička, M., Kašpar, V., Piacková, V., Sudová, E., Linhart, O., 2010. A review on the potential of triploid tench for aquaculture. *Rev. Fish. Biol. Fish.* 20, 317–329.
- Fortes-Silva, R., Martínez, F.J., Villarroel, M., Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., 2010. Daily rhythms of locomotor activity, feeding behavior and dietary selection in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. Part A: Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 156 (4), 445–450.
- Fraser, D.F., Gilliam, J.F., Akkara, J.T., Albanese, B.W., Snider, S.B., 2004. Night feeding by guppies under predator release: effects on growth and daytime courtship. *Ecology* 85 (2), 312–319.
- Fraser, N.H., Metcalfe, N.B., Thorpe, J.E., 1993. Temperature-dependent switch between diurnal and nocturnal foraging in salmon. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. B: Biol. Sci.* 252 (1334), 135–139.
- Gela, D., Flajshans, M., Kocour, M., Rodina, M., Linhart, O., 2006. Tench (*Tinca tinca*) broodstock management in breeding station under conditions of pond culture: a review. *Aquac. Int.* 14 (1), 195–203.

- Gregory, C.G.M. (2022). Utilising Chronobiology for Sustainable Aquaculture Nutrition & Fish Health (Doctoral dissertation, Bangor University (United Kingdom)).
- Hamilton, F., 1822. An Account of the Fishes Found in the River Ganges and its Branches, (Vol. 1). Archibald Constable.
- Hamilton, T.J., Szaszkievicz, J., Krook, J., Richards, J.G., Stiller, K., Brauner, C.J., 2022. Continuous light (relative to a 12:12 photoperiod) has no effect on anxiety-like behaviour, boldness, and locomotion in coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) post-smolts in recirculating aquaculture systems at a salinity of either 2.5 or 10 ppt. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. Part A: Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 263, 111070.
- Hammond, T.T., Palme, R., Lacey, E.A., 2018. Ecological specialization, variability in activity patterns and response to environmental change. *Biol. Lett.* 14 (6), 20180115.
- Haney, J.F., 1988. Diel patterns of zooplankton behavior. *Bull. Mar. Sci.* 43 (3), 583–603.
- Herrero, M.J., Madrid, J.A., Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., 2003. Entrainment to light of circadian activity rhythms in tench (*Tinca tinca*). *Chronobiol. Int.* 20 (6), 1001–1017.
- Kotler, B.P., Brown, J.S., Hasson, O., 1991. Factors affecting gerbil foraging behavior and rates of owl predation. *Ecology* 72 (6), 2249–2260.
- Krylov, V.V., Izvekov, E.I., Pavlova, V.V., Pankova, N.A., Osipova, E.A., 2021. Circadian rhythms in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) behaviour and the sources of their variability. *Biol. Rev.* 96 (3), 785–797.
- Levin, E.D., Bencan, Z., Cerutti, D.T., 2007. Anxiolytic effects of nicotine in zebrafish. *Physiol. Behav.* 90 (1), 54–58.
- López-Olmeda, J.F., Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., 2010. Feeding rhythms in fish: from behavioral to molecular approach. *Biol. Clock Fish.* 8, 155–183.
- López-Olmeda, J.F., Blanco-Vives, B., Pujante, I.M., Wunderink, Y.S., Mancera, J.M., Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., 2013. Daily rhythms in the hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal axis and acute stress responses in a teleost flatfish, *Solea senegalensis*. *Chronobiol. Int.* 30 (4), 530–539.
- Martins, C.L., Galhardo, L., Noble, C., Damsgård, B., Spedicato, M.T., Zupa, W., Beauchaud, M., Kulczykowska, E., Massabuau, J.-C., Carter, T., Planellas, S.R., Kristiansen, T., 2012. Behavioural indicators of welfare in farmed fish. *Fish. Physiol. Biochem.* 38, 17–41.
- Maximino, C., de Brito, T.M., da Silva Batista, A.W., Herculano, A.M., Morato, S., Gouveia Jr, A., 2010. Measuring anxiety in zebrafish: a critical review. *Behav. Brain Res.* 214 (2), 157–171.
- Maximino, C., Benzecry, R., Oliveira, K.R.M., Batista, E.D.J.O., Herculano, A.M., Rosemberg, D.B., Blaser, R., 2012. A comparison of the light/dark and novel tank tests in zebrafish. *Behaviour* 149 (10–12), 1099–1123.
- McNeil, R., Benoît, R., Desgranges, J.L., 1993. Daytime and nighttime activity at a breeding colony of Great Blue Herons in a nontidal environment. *Can. J. Zool.* 71 (6), 1075–1078.
- Metcalfe, N.B., Fraser, N.H., Burns, M.D., 1998. State-dependent shifts between nocturnal and diurnal activity in salmon. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. B: Biol. Sci.* 265 (1405), 1503–1507.
- Monterroso, P., Alves, P.C., Ferreras, P., 2013. Catch me if you can: diel activity patterns of mammalian prey and predators. *Ethology* 119 (12), 1044–1056.
- Mutak A. Cosinor2: Extended tools for cosinor analysis of rhythms; 2018. R package version 0.2.1. (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=cosinor2>).
- Nelson, W., 1979. Methods for cosinor-rhythmometry. *Chronobiologia* 6, 305–323.
- Oliveira, A.R., Cabrera-Álvarez, M.J., Soares, F., Díaz-Gil, C., Candeias-Mendes, A., Saraiva, J.L., Arechavala-Lopez, P., 2024. Structural enrichment promotes natural behaviour and welfare of captive gilthead seabream broodstock. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 275, 106289.
- Ota, S.M., Suchecki, D., Meerlo, P., 2018. Chronic social defeat stress suppresses locomotor activity but does not affect the free-running circadian period of the activity rhythm in mice. *Neurobiol. Sleep. Circadian Rhythms* 5, 1–7.
- Pinheiro, J., Bates, D., DebRoy, S., Sarkar, D., Heisterkamp, S., Van Willigen, B., Maintainer, R., 2017. Package 'nlme'. Linear and nonlinear mixed effects models. *R. Package Version* 3, 1–131.
- Pinkiewicz, T.H., Purser, G.J., Williams, R.N., 2011. A computer vision system to analyse the swimming behaviour of farmed fish in commercial aquaculture facilities: a case study using cage-held Atlantic salmon. *Aquac. Eng.* 45 (1), 20–27.
- Pintos, S., Cavallino, L., Yañez, A.V., Pandolfi, M., Pozzi, A.G., 2021. Effects of intraspecific chemical cues on the behaviour of the bloodfin tetra *Aphyocharax anisitsi* (Ostariophysi: Characidae). *Behav. Process.* 193, 104533.
- Pintos, S., Lucon-Xiccato, T., Vera, L.M., Bertolucci, C., 2023. Daily rhythms in the behavioural stress response of the zebrafish *Danio rerio*. *Physiol. Behav.* 268, 114241.
- Pintos, S., Lucon-Xiccato, T., Vera, L.M., Conceição, L., Bertolucci, C., Sánchez-Vázquez, J., Rema, P., 2024. Social buffering of behavioural stress response in two fish species, Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and koi carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *Ethology*, e13464.
- Qiu, X., Nomichi, S., Chen, K., Honda, M., Kang, I.J., Shimasaki, Y., Oshima, Y., 2017. Short-term and persistent impacts on behaviors related to locomotion, anxiety, and startle responses of Japanese medaka (*Oryzias latipes*) induced by acute, sublethal exposure to chlorpyrifos. *Aquat. Toxicol.* 192, 148–154.
- Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., López-Olmeda, J.F., Vera Andujar, L.M., 2019. Fish welfare and biological rhythms: time to regulate. *A Derecho Anim.: Forum Anim. Law Stud.* 10 (4), 93–97, pp. 00.
- Sanders, D., Frago, E., Kehoe, R., Patterson, C., Gaston, K.J., 2021. A meta-analysis of biological impacts of artificial light at night. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 5 (1), 74–81.
- Silva, R.F., Pinho, B.R., Santos, M.M., Oliveira, J.M., 2022. Disruptions of circadian rhythms, sleep, and stress responses in zebrafish: New infrared-based activity monitoring assays for toxicity assessment. *Chemosphere* 305, 135449.
- Tambling, C.J., Minnie, L., Meyer, J., Freeman, E.W., Santymire, R.M., Adendorff, J., Kerley, G.I., 2015. Temporal shifts in activity of prey following large predator reintroductions. *Behav. Ecol. Sociobiol.* 69, 1153–1161.
- Thompson, R.R., Paul, E.S., Radford, A.N., Purser, J., Mendl, M., 2016. Routine handling methods affect behaviour of three-spined sticklebacks in a novel test of anxiety. *Behav. Brain Res.* 306, 26–35.
- Thoré, E.S., Brendonck, L., Pincheel, T., 2021. Natural daily patterns in fish behaviour may confound results of ecotoxicological testing. *Environ. Pollut.* 276, 116738.
- Thoré, E.S., Aulsebrook, A.E., Brand, J.A., Almeida, R.A., Brodin, T., Bertram, M.G., 2024. Time is of the essence: The importance of considering biological rhythms in an increasingly polluted world. *Plos Biol.* 22 (1), e3002478.
- Tran, S., T Gerlai, R., 2016. The novel tank test: handling stress and the context specific psychopharmacology of anxiety. *Curr. Psychopharmacol.* 5 (2), 169–179.
- Vaze, K.M., Sharma, V.K., 2013. On the adaptive significance of circadian clocks for their owners. *Chronobiol. Int.* 30 (4), 413–433.
- Vera, L.M., López-Olmeda, J.F., Bayarri, M.J., Madrid, J.A., Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., 2005. Influence of light intensity on plasma melatonin and locomotor activity rhythms in tench. *Chronobiol. Int.* 22 (1), 67–78.
- Vera, L.M., Montoya, A., Pujante, I.M., Pérez-Sánchez, J., Caldich-Giner, J.A., Mancera, J.M., Sánchez-Vázquez, F.J., 2014. Acute stress response in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata* L.) is time-of-day dependent: physiological and oxidative stress indicators. *Chronobiol. Int.* 31 (9), 1051–1061.
- Verma, P., Hellemans, K.G., Choi, F.Y., Yu, W., Weinberg, J., 2010. Circadian phase and sex effects on depressive/anxiety-like behaviors and HPA axis responses to acute stress. *Physiol. Behav.* 99 (3), 276–285.
- Walbaum, J.J., 1792. Petri Arredi sueci genera piscium. In quibus systema totum ichthyologiae proponitur cum classibus, ordinibus, generum characteribus, specierum differentiis, observationibus plurimis. Redactis speciebus 242 ad genera 52. Ichthyologiae pars III. Ant. Ferdin. Rose, Grypeswaldiae [Greifswald]. *Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.) Zool. Pt.*
- Wong, K., Elegante, M., Bartels, B., Elkhayat, S., Tien, D., Roy, S., Kalueff, A.V., 2010. Analyzing habituation responses to novelty in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *Behav. Brain Res.* 208 (2), 450–457.
- Zhang, C., Ma, J., Qi, Q., Xu, M., Xu, R., 2023. Effects of ammonia exposure on anxiety behavior, oxidative stress and inflammation in guppy (*Poecilia reticulata*). *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. Part C: Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 265, 109539.
- Zhdanova, I.V., Reeb, S.G., 2005. Circadian rhythms in fish. *Fish. Physiol.* 24, 197–238.